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- Poetry
- Short Stories
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“TEACHING DRAFTING TO BTVTED DRAFTING STUDENTS: SHAPING THE FOUNDATION OF TECHNICAL SKILLS”

Teaching Drafting to students who are enrolled in the Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education (BTVTED) major in Drafting is both a challenge and a privilege since it requires technical knowledge and pedagogy. Technical knowledge and strategies in teaching are bot significant in teaching Drafting because the students will be future educators, they should be knowledgeable enough to use different technical tools in drafting and also enough competency for their students to learn efficiently.

These future educators must show their learners how this technical knowledge will be used in real-life situations. They must be able to emphasize that the things that we see around from the simple things like tables, chairs, houses to complex things like buildings with different structural designs, bridges, and machinery came from simple drafts. Integrating industry-based examples and actual drafting projects encourages learners to apply theories and techniques in real-world contexts making the subject more meaningful. Another method that can be used in teaching Drafting is integrating traditional and modern strategies. Manual drafting helps the learners develop precision and discipline while Computer-Aided Design (CAD) helps them to work their speed and adaptability to advanced technology. Moreover, since BTVTED students are future educators, there must be focus on the pedagogy because they will be imparting these skills to their future students, they must effectively and efficiently transfer the knowledge and skills to their future students.

Through these strategies, drafting students will not only master the subject but also be able to impart the knowledge and skills to their future students. It may be a challenge but if done right they will be successful in the long run.

